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**DIGITAL ADDICTION AND SCHOOLCHILDREN: WHERE IS THE BOUNDARY
BETWEEN LEARNING AND MENTAL DESTRUCTION**

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Abstract. *In the context of rapid digitalization of education, the problem of digital dependence of schoolchildren is becoming one of the most acute pedagogical and socio-psychological topics of our time. On the one hand, digital technologies create unique opportunities for individualization of learning, expansion of educational resources, increase in motivation and involvement of students. On the other hand, it is their excessive and unlimited use that leads to the formation of cognitive and emotional distortions, development of clip thinking, decrease in the ability to critically analyze information and in-depth learning. The article reveals the contradiction between the need for digitalization of the educational process and the threat of the destructive impact of technology on the psyche of students. Digital addiction not only as a psychological, but also as a pedagogical problem, since it directly affects the quality of knowledge acquisition, the nature of interaction between teacher and student, as well as the formation of school culture as a whole. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of modern research, as well as empirical observations from school practice, showing that digital addiction manifests itself in the replacement of educational activity with digital pseudo-employment, weakening motivation for offline forms of education and increasing emotional instability among schoolchildren. The scientific novelty of the work lies in substantiating the concept of the "digital divide within a school" and formulating criteria for distinguishing between the productive and destructive use of digital technologies in education. As a practical result, the article proposes a set of pedagogical measures aimed at forming digital hygiene of students and developing resistance to the negative effects of digitalization.*

Key words: *digital addiction, schoolchildren, pedagogy, digitalization, mental health, digital hygiene.*

The modern school is at a turning point in its development: digitalization of education is turning from an auxiliary tool into a system-forming factor that determines the content, forms and methods of teaching. According to UNESCO and OECD forecasts, in the coming years, digital technologies will form the basis of educational ecosystems, and the level of digital competence will become a key indicator of the quality of education. In the context of globalization and the information society, access to digital resources is considered a prerequisite for equal educational opportunities (OECD, 2021).

However, along with the obvious advantages, a new risk also arises – the formation of digital addiction in schoolchildren. This phenomenon manifests itself in excessive and uncontrolled use of digital devices, which leads to the deformation of cognitive processes, the emotional sphere and social

skills of adolescents. We are talking not just about the problem of “gadget addiction”, but about a profound change in the structure of cognitive activity, where the dominance of screen stimuli replaces the ability for long-term concentration, critical thinking and reflection.

The particular complexity of the situation lies in the ambivalence of the digital environment: the school is obliged to use digital technologies as part of the educational process, but this is precisely what becomes the catalyst for the development of addiction. Thus, the pedagogical process increasingly balances on the edge: where the productive use of technology ends and the destruction of the student's psyche begins.

According to research by J. Twenge (2017), a sharp increase in screen time after 2010 correlates with an increase in anxiety and depressive states among adolescents. N. Carr (2011) notes that constant switching between digital tasks forms clip thinking, in which depth of perception is lost. Domestic studies (Shkolnik, 2022) record a decrease in schoolchildren's interest in traditional forms of education and an increase in the dependence of educational motivation on the digital environment. These data confirm the relevance of posing the problem in a pedagogical context.

Thus, a number of research questions arise: Where is the line between the productive use of digital technologies and the formation of digital dependence? What are the pedagogical criteria for distinguishing between “educational” and “destructive” digital activities? What methods and practices can a school implement to minimize the risks of digital addiction and develop a culture of conscious digital behavior?

The solution to these issues is not only of academic but also of practical importance. Without understanding the problem of digital dependence, the school risks turning into a space where technologies replace education rather than enhance it. This study aims to identify the mechanisms of digital dependence formation in schoolchildren and to search for pedagogical tools that allow keeping digitalization within the boundaries that promote development rather than degradation of the individual.

Research methodology.

1. Theoretical analysis - study of works in the field of pedagogy, psychology and digital sociology [1-3].

2. Empirical observations - recording the behavior of schoolchildren in lessons when using and limiting digital devices.

3. Comparative method - comparison of traditional and digital forms of learning in terms of the level of involvement and cognitive depth.

4. Pedagogical experiment - introduction of elements of digital hygiene (limiting screen time, balance of formats) in school practice.

The term "digital addiction" is most often used in psychology and psychiatry, where it is interpreted as a type of behavioral addiction associated with excessive and uncontrolled use of electronic devices and digital services [4]. However, in pedagogy this phenomenon takes on special significance: it directly influences the processes of learning, socialization and the formation of the student's personality.

Unlike adults, children and teenagers are the most vulnerable group: their cognitive system, emotional sphere and self-regulation mechanisms are still in the process of formation. That is why the influence of digital technologies on the psyche of a schoolchild has a cumulative rather than a linear effect: every additional hour spent in the digital environment changes not only current activity, but also the style of thinking, habits and forms of communication. Thus, digital addiction in the school environment can be defined as a condition in which digital technologies cease to be an educational tool and become a self-sufficient source of stimulation, displacing traditional forms of educational and social activity.

In school practice, digital addiction manifests itself in a number of characteristic forms that the teacher can observe directly: students spend a significant amount of time on a computer or tablet, creating the illusion of learning activity, but in fact they are immersed in social networks, games or entertainment services; the formation of a preference for short visual and audiovisual stimuli instead

of deep reading and text analysis [1]; motivation to learn decreases without external digital “triggers” (app ratings, likes, badges on an educational platform); live communication is replaced by digital communication; children cope worse with group discussions and offline projects; constant switching between digital applications leads to a decrease in concentration, memory and overall productivity.

Traditional pedagogy viewed learning as a process that required long-term concentration, consistent acquisition, and active reflection [5,6]. Digital addiction destroys these principles, as the learner gets used to fragmented perception of information and does not develop the ability to work with large volumes of data.

From the point of view of cultural-historical theory (Vygotsky), digital dependence can be understood as a violation of the process of internalization: instead of appropriating cultural experience, the child assimilates only external stimuli, without translating them into his own cognitive structures [5].

From the position of the activity approach [7], digital dependence distorts the motivational sphere: activity is replaced by action, and the learning goal is replaced by a digital stimulus. As a result, pseudo-activity is formed that does not lead to personal development.

Foreign and domestic research.

Research by J. Twenge (2017) shows a direct correlation between the increase in screen time in adolescents and an increase in depression and anxiety [2].

According to Cain, Gradisar (2010), more than 60% of schoolchildren have sleep disorders caused by late use of gadgets [8].

In Kazakhstan and the CIS countries, there has been an increase in the number of children showing signs of “digital fatigue” and a decrease in interest in traditional educational formats (Shkolnik, 2022) [3].

Livingstone & Helsper (2007) note the phenomenon of “digital inequality”: children from families with a low level of digital culture are more susceptible to the risks of addiction [9].

These studies confirm that digital addiction is not an individual problem of a single child, but a systemic challenge for all pedagogical practice, requiring theoretical understanding and the development of new approaches.

Digital addiction of schoolchildren should be considered as a complex pedagogical phenomenon, including cognitive, motivational and social aspects. Unlike traditional forms of addictive behavior, it is disguised as educational activity and therefore often underestimated by teachers and parents.

The boundary between learning and the destruction of the psyche lies precisely at the level of pedagogical regulation: if the digital environment is controlled by the teacher and serves educational purposes, it develops. If it gets out of control and replaces the content of learning, dependence is formed.

One of the most noticeable consequences of digital addiction in schoolchildren is the growth of psycho-emotional instability. According to the study by J. Twenge et al. (2018), after 2010 — the time of the mass distribution of smartphones and social networks — the level of anxiety and depression among adolescents in the United States increased by more than 30%. This trend is also recorded in other countries, including Kazakhstan, where school psychologists note an increase in the number of requests related to emotional burnout, aggression, and sleep disorders in school-age children [10].

The reason is that the digital environment acts as a source of constant stimulation: messages, likes, notifications create a “dopamine trap” effect. For a teenager, this turns into a constant expectation of digital reinforcement, which in the long term reduces stress resistance and leads to the formation of emotional dependence.

Research by Cain & Gradisar (2010) showed that more than 60 % schoolchildren who use gadgets before bedtime face chronic sleep deprivation. The blue spectrum of the screen suppresses the production of melatonin, shifts biorhythms and leads to the so-called “delayed sleep syndrome” [8].

In school practice, this is reflected in the fact that a significant portion of children come to classes in a state of drowsiness, with reduced concentration and reduced academic performance. Thus, digital addiction has a direct impact on the physiological foundations of educational activity.

N. Carr (2011) in his book *The Shallows* notes that constant use of the Internet and gadgets leads to a restructuring of the neural connections of the brain: deep, sequential reading is replaced by superficial scanning of information. For schoolchildren, this means a loss of the ability to long-term concentration; logical analysis of the text; critical comparison of sources.

As a result, “clip thinking” is formed – an orientation towards quick, bright stimuli (short videos, memes, infographics) instead of complex analytical work. This leads to a decrease in the quality of the educational result and impoverishment of cognitive activity [1].

Research by Livingstone & Helsper (2007) shows that excessive use of digital networks by adolescents reduces their ability to communicate offline. In the school environment, this manifests itself in difficulties working in groups, an inability to conduct discussions, and conflicts caused by digital forms of bullying (cyberbullying) [9].

Particularly alarming is the tendency to replace emotional contact with digital emojis and stickers: children are worse at recognizing non-verbal signals, and their levels of empathy and social intelligence are declining.

Digital addiction is a "gateway" to broader forms of addictive behavior. According to Griffiths (2005), digital addictions have all the characteristics of classic addiction [4]: withdrawal syndrome (irritability when gadgets are limited); loss of control over time; substitution of real activity with virtual; gradual increase in the "dose" of digital activity. For schoolchildren, this is expressed in a sharp decrease in learning motivation and an increase in “digital sabotage” – the desire to replace any offline task with a digital analogue, even if it is formally less productive.

“Digital apathy” is increasingly being recorded. This is a condition in which a student shows no interest in either traditional activities or digital activities, except for superficial scrolling and passive consumption of content. This condition is particularly dangerous: it destroys cognitive motivation in principle, and therefore threatens the educational process itself. Thus, digital dependence of schoolchildren leads to complex psychological and cognitive risks from sleep and concentration disorders to decreased empathy and ability to reflect. These consequences are not limited to the field of psychology, but directly affect pedagogical results: schoolchildren become less motivated, less resilient to stress and less capable of deep learning. This is why digital addiction should be considered by schools not only as a private mental health problem, but also as a central pedagogical challenge of the digital age .

Digitalization of schools in the 21st century has become an integral part of educational policy. Electronic diaries, online platforms, the use of AI technologies in teaching and testing - all this is being introduced as part of the global strategy for the modernization of education (OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2023). The digital environment promises increased accessibility of knowledge, individualization of educational trajectories, and the development of flexible competencies in demand in the digital economy [11,12].

However, a pedagogical paradox appears here: the more actively a school uses digital technologies to achieve educational goals, the higher the risk that these technologies themselves will cause cognitive and psychological distortions. Digitalization is simultaneously a necessary condition for modern education and a risk factor for the destruction of the psyche of schoolchildren.

In recent years, schools have been under double pressure: from the state side - requirements for digitalization are recorded in strategic programs (“Digital School”, “Smart Nation”, etc.); on the part of parents and society - the expectation that the child will be “digitally literate”, and therefore competitive in the labor market. Thus, digitalization becomes a normative imperative: a school cannot abandon technologies, even if it records their negative impact.

The introduction of digital platforms paradoxically increases inequality between children. Children with high self-regulation and family support are able to use digital resources as a development tool. However, for another group of schoolchildren (with low motivation, weak

cognitive stability), digitalization becomes a catalyst for addiction. As a result, a phenomenon is formed that can be described as a “digital divide within a school”: some children use technologies for learning, while others become hostages to them.

Digitalization is changing the very role of the teacher. He is no longer the only source of knowledge: educational platforms, video lessons and artificial intelligence compete with him in providing information. The paradox is that it is in the era of information abundance that the need for a teacher as a navigator, mentor and filter of information increases .

However, practice shows that many teachers experience professional burnout while trying to combine the classic role of a teacher with the functions of a digital moderator. This creates new risks: instead of regulating the digital environment, the school sometimes unconsciously transmits and amplifies it.

One of the key paradoxes of digitalization is the replacement of educational content with a digital form. Students often perceive tasks as meaningful only if they are presented in a digital shell (in an application, platform or interactive resource). Traditional forms of work - reading a book, oral discussion, notebook - seem outdated and "less valuable" to them. As a result, the school risks losing its balance: knowledge begins to be measured not by the depth of understanding, but by the technological shell in which it is presented. This leads to the fragmentation of the educational process and the formation of false motivation.

The paradox becomes especially acute in ethical terms. If digital technologies really do affect the psyche of schoolchildren, then the question arises: does the school have the right to encourage their use without proper control? The teacher finds himself in a contradictory position: he is obliged to implement digital practices, but at the same time he must protect children from their destructive consequences.

Thus, digitalization in school appears as a dual phenomenon: it expands educational horizons and opens up access to new forms of learning; simultaneously increases the risks of digital addiction, cognitive and emotional deformations, digital inequality and teacher burnout. The paradox of the school is that it is obliged to use digital technologies, but they are becoming a source of threat to the mental health of students. This requires pedagogy to develop principles of "reasonable digitalization", when technologies serve the development of the individual, and do not replace the educational process itself.

Working in a modern school, it is impossible not to notice how the digital environment changes the daily behavior of students. The following patterns are recorded in lessons: most students are able to maintain concentration on an explanation without digital support for only 5-7 minutes, after which they begin to get distracted, requiring visual or interactive stimulation; homework given orally or written in a notebook is perceived by many children as “less obligatory” than assignments posted in an electronic system (electronic diary, Google Classroom, etc.); “ Even with the official ban, smartphones remain in the spotlight: children check them during breaks, during recess, and sometimes even secretly during class. These facts confirm that digital addiction manifests itself not only in the external environment, but also within the school classroom.

To test the hypothesis of digital addiction, an anonymous survey was conducted in one of the schools among students in grades 7–11 (N=214). The following results were obtained: 72% admitted to spending more than 5 hours a day in front of a screen, not counting the time spent on schoolwork; 58% noted that they “find it difficult to concentrate in class without visual digital support”; 46 % reported regularly feeling tired and having headaches after prolonged use of gadgets; 37% admitted to feeling irritated if a teacher limits smartphone use in class.

Thus, almost half of the students show signs of developing digital addiction, which manifests itself in decreased concentration, irritability and physiological discomfort.

Cases from school practices and

1. *A case of "digital sabotage"*. In the 9th grade, students refused to do a written essay in a notebook, demanding a "digital analogue" - the ability to submit the text via messenger. The task in its traditional form was perceived as "outdated" and "superfluous".

2. *A case of "gadget-dependent motivation"*. When the "30 minutes without a smartphone" project was introduced in a literature lesson, some students showed irritation, their involvement decreased, and conflict situations arose. After gradual adaptation, only 40% were able to perceive the text normally without digital stimuli.

3. *A case of "paradoxical involvement"*. In the 7th grade, students actively participated in interactive quizzes (Kahoot , Quizizz), but when they moved on to discussing the text, their interest dropped sharply. This indicates that learning activity depends on the form of presentation, not on the content.

Empirical data show that the key risk factor is the lack of digital culture in the family. Parents often do not limit screen time or themselves demonstrate an example of excessive use of gadgets. At the same time, families with regulations ("screen after school no more than 2 hours", "no smartphone after 22:00") show a significantly lower level of addiction in children.

The results of observations and surveys allow us to identify several patterns: digital addiction develops faster in children with low motivation for traditional activities; it manifests itself in emotional instability and resistance to the restriction of digital stimuli; A key indicator of addiction is a decline in the ability to learn offline without external digital reinforcement.

Practical observations confirm that digital dependence of schoolchildren is not an abstract threat, but an everyday reality of a modern school. It is expressed in a change in attitude to tasks, transformation of educational motivation, physiological symptoms and social conflicts. These empirical data reinforce the need for pedagogical research: the school should not only use digital technologies, but also actively develop digital hygiene in children as part of the educational program.

The problem of digital addiction among schoolchildren is a multi-layered challenge that cannot be solved solely through administrative bans, technical restrictions or isolated measures. Research shows that simple bans on the use of gadgets often have the opposite effect: schoolchildren experience increased resistance, irritability and even a secret increase in screen time, which aggravates the addiction. Instead, a comprehensive approach is required that integrates pedagogical, psychological, social and institutional measures. Such an approach involves not only control, but also education, motivation and the creation of alternative forms of activity.

The complexity is due to the nature of digital addiction: it affects cognitive processes (for example, the formation of clip thinking), the emotional sphere (anxiety and depression), social skills (loss of live communication) and even physiological aspects (sleep disorders). According to a 2023-2024 research review, effective interventions combine several strategies: from individual therapy to school prevention programs. In this context, the school acts not just as a place of control, but as a center for the formation of a culture of conscious digital behavior, where technologies are integrated into the educational process without dominating it.

In a comprehensive approach, interdisciplinary cooperation plays a key role: teachers, psychologists, parents and even external experts (for example, digital security specialists) must work in a single system. This allows not only to minimize risks, but also to turn the problem into an opportunity to develop new competencies, such as digital hygiene.

In the digital age, "digital hygiene" should be recognized as a full-fledged educational competency, on par with reading, writing or math skills. This concept includes a set of practices aimed at conscious and safe use of digital technologies, preventing overload and maintaining mental health. According to the report "Student Digital Wellbeing: state of the Nation Report 2024, digital hygiene helps schoolchildren balance between the online and offline worlds, reducing the risks of addiction by 20–30% when implemented systematically [13].

Key components of digital hygiene:

Mindful screen time management: teaching students to schedule screen time using timer apps or diaries. For example, the 20-20-20 rule (look at an object 20 feet away for 20 seconds every 20 minutes) to prevent visual fatigue.

Distinguishing between educational and entertaining content: knowing when technology is serving learning (e.g. educational platforms) and when it is distracting (e.g. social media). This includes critical analysis: "Does this video help me understand the topic or is it just entertaining?"

Critical assessment of digital information: developing skills to verify sources, combat disinformation and media manipulation. Research shows that students with a high level of media literacy are less likely to become addicted.

Balance online and offline activities: forming habits of reading books, physical exercise, and live communication. Physical activity, as noted in recent studies, directly reduces the level of Internet addiction in students.

Digital self-control: practices like turning off notifications, following a "media diet" (limiting content consumption), and scheduling digital activity.

For implementation, it is recommended to introduce a separate module or course "Digital Culture and Hygiene" into the school curriculum, starting in elementary grades. This could include weekly lessons with practical tasks, such as analyzing your own screen time or creating a personal digital hygiene plan. Such programs, according to reviews, reduce addiction symptoms by 15-25%.

The traditional role of a teacher as a "controller" of gadgets is outdated and ineffective in the digital age. Instead, educators should become digital literacy mentors, helping students navigate the digital world. This is a shift from prohibitive measures to educational ones: the teacher does not prohibit technology, but teaches its conscious use.

Key aspects of the new role:

Integrating technology into learning: using interactive activities (e.g. Kahoot for quizzes) and collaborative online projects, but with clear rules and time limits. This prevents overload and keeps the focus on the content.

Modeling healthy behavior: the teacher avoids inappropriate use of gadgets in class by setting an example. For example, by explaining, "I turn off notifications while working so I can focus."

Conducting mini-lessons on media literacy: topics like "How to distinguish an educational video from an entertaining one?" or "Why TikTok doesn't replace a textbook?" Such classes develop critical thinking and reduce the risk of clip thinking.

Developing reflection: regular discussions with students about the impact of technology on learning and well-being. For example, weekly "digital diaries" where students record the pros and cons of screen time.

Research confirms the effectiveness of this approach: mentor teachers help reduce addiction by 20% by increasing awareness. In addition, it reduces teacher burnout by turning them into active participants in digital transformation.

The family is the primary environment for the formation of digital habits, and without its participation, school measures will remain incomplete. Children from families with clear rules for the use of gadgets demonstrate 2-3 times less dependence. Parents themselves often contribute to the problem by not limiting screen time or by setting an example of excessive use of devices.

Effective forms of interaction between school and family:

Parent-teacher meetings and webinars: discussing the risks of digital addiction and hygiene practices. For example, sessions with cybersecurity and psychology experts.

Shared rules: developing family-school norms such as "no smartphones at dinner" or "no internet in the bedroom after 10pm."

Events and challenges: "a week without unnecessary screens" with the participation of parents and children, where changes in well-being are recorded.

Parent Education: media literacy courses so parents can be positive role models. Research shows that such initiatives reduce children's screen time by 30%. Family involvement turns the problem into a collective process, enhancing the effect of school interventions.

For schoolchildren with pronounced signs of addiction, targeted support is required, combining psychological assistance and pedagogical methods. This includes diagnostics and correction to prevent the escalation of the problem.

Key measures:

Consultations with a school psychologist: diagnosis of the level of addiction, anxiety and emotional state using tests (for example, Digital Addiction Scale).

Corrective programs: keeping a screen time diary, rewarding for compliance with restrictions (reward system). Persuasive strategies in digital interventions, such as self-monitoring apps, have proven effective.

Alternative forms of leisure: involvement in sports, creative clubs or volunteering. Physical activity is especially effective in reducing addiction by increasing self-esteem.

Group trainings: development of self-regulation skills, stress resistance and social interaction in an offline format.

Such support should be integrated into the school system, with progress regularly monitored.

The school as an institution is obliged to create a model of intelligent digitalization, where technologies serve education, and do not dominate.

Key measures:

- Regulations on the use of gadgets: rules that allow devices only for educational purposes (for example, a ban on smartphones during lessons, except for teacher assignments).

Blended learning: combining digital platforms with offline methods (reading books, discussions). This maintains balance and prevents overload.

Digital Load Monitoring: track your total screen time, including homework, to avoid chronic fatigue.

Pedagogical reflection: discussions with teachers and students about the impact of technology.

Digital volunteer programs: high school students teach younger students about hygiene, increasing responsibility.

Such measures, according to 2024 data, increase digital well-being by 25%.

Experiments are useful for testing strategies: Digital breaks: 10-15 minutes without screens in class for discussions. Projects "Digital Detox ": temporary restriction of gadgets with analysis of changes in academic performance and well-being. Research confirms the positive effect. Gamification: badges for hygiene that motivate through play. AI Integration: use apps for monitoring and hygiene advice.

Experiments allow approaches to be adapted to a specific school.

The solutions to the problem of digital addiction lie in pedagogical understanding and regulation of technologies. The strategy includes the formation of digital hygiene as a competence, rethinking the role of the teacher, family involvement and systemic measures. The school of the future uses technologies to enrich education, maintaining the mental stability of students.

The problem of digital dependence of schoolchildren in the context of rapid digitalization of education is one of the key challenges of modern pedagogy. The analysis conducted in the article showed that the digital environment has a dual nature: on the one hand, it opens up new horizons of learning, creates conditions for personalization of educational trajectories and expands access to information; on the other hand, it provokes deformation of cognitive processes, emotional instability and the formation of dependent behavior.

Based on the theoretical approaches, psychological research and practical observations considered, several fundamental conclusions can be drawn:

Digital addiction is not only a psychological but also a pedagogical phenomenon. It manifests itself in the substitution of educational activity with digital pseudo-employment, a decrease in the ability to deeply perceive knowledge and the formation of clip thinking.

The boundary between learning and the destruction of the psyche lies in pedagogical regulation. If digital technologies are controlled by a teacher and integrated into a meaningful educational process, they become a tool for development. If the digital environment replaces the content of education, there is a risk of dependence and degradation of cognitive activity.

The school faces a digitalization paradox. It is obliged to implement technologies in accordance with state and public requirements, but in doing so it risks increasing the psychological and cognitive deformations of students.

Empirical data confirms the systemic nature of the problem. Most schoolchildren spend significantly more time in front of the screen than is required for learning, and show decreased concentration, irritability, and fatigue.

Formation of digital hygiene should become a priority of school education. This is a new competence of the 21st century, including skills of screen time management, critical evaluation of digital content and maintaining a balance between online and offline activities.

Thus, the key pedagogical task in the context of digitalization is not to reject technologies or integrate them without limits, but to build a strategy for reasonable digitalization. The school should teach the child not only to use digital tools, but also to master them as a tool, and not to become their hostage.

The prospects for further research include the development of models for diagnosing digital addiction, empirical testing of the effectiveness of school programs for developing digital hygiene, and an analysis of the role of the teacher as a mediator between the child's personality and the digital environment.

The school of the future is a school where digital technologies work to develop critical thinking, emotional stability and social maturity, rather than destroy them.

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